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TEACHER AS AN AGENT OF SOCIAL CHANGE

Education

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Abstract

The present study was carried out to study their difficulties and problems in their school environment (financial, administrable, political, spatial, lack) of facilities, poor supervision, bureaucratic role of supervising staff and discouragement etc. and in their rural area from A sample 150 teachers working in the schools of rural area of Jammu was selected randomly which hinder their effective functions as agents of social change in rural area of Jammu. The results reveal that most of the teachers are not satisfied with their present economic conditions. Further said that the economic development in the rural area of Jammu is also a reverse factor which is hindering the required social change and many social evils such as drinking and dowry is increasing day by day in rural area of Jammu.

Key Words: Education, Social change, Teacher etc.

Introduction

In modern education, it is considered important to study social change from the point of view of social progress because education is considered to be an agent of social change. In the olden days when society was very much bound by its traditions and there were little opportunities for change, education tried to conserve what was achieved through the passage of time. But in the modern world due to inventions and discoveries there is a rapid change in modern society. Changes are so rapid that education must adjust its progress and plans to meet the demands of new situations.

Social change implies not only the change of outer form of a community or a society but also in the social institution as well as the ideas of the people living in that society. In other words, social change is a term is applied to change in the material aspects of life as well as in the idea, values and attitudes of the people.

The main objective of the social change is to promote "All sided development of the village community including their economic, political, social, cultural and moral development". To make the village self-sufficient in the primary needs of life such as food, clothing and shelter and to promote the development of the local area is also one of the main objectives of social change. If we want to bring about a social change in rural area we must develop the village and its people. The teacher has to play a important role in the process of social change. He must know the changes taking place in the society. The reason is that the value and the pace of change affect the educational system of a society. A teacher must know the factors responsible for change, the effect of those changes on the life of children and other people and finally how education tries to meet the challenges of these changes.

As a matter of fact, people resist change; they feel secure in their old way of living. A study of the history of material and social investments will indicates that inventions were not accepted readily by the people. We all know that the vaccination, the use of railways, education for women has been opposed. Even today the benefits of family planning are doubted and people are suspicious of many and economic change that are being brought. The point to remember is that an invention introduces

some kind of change in the life and environment of the people and this change is resisted unless ground has been prepared for it.

The teacher is in a unique position to prepare that climate of opinion which is necessary before a new scheme is introduced. The teacher and a few other important leaders of the community have to be convinced in regard to the benefits that are to come by adopting a particular measure of social change. Education can be well utilized through the agency of village teacher for preparing the people to accept given social and economic reform.

Thus it is imperative on the planners that before a programme is put into practice, it should be tried on a small scale and its results should be observed. It is also necessary to educate the public opinion and nothing is perfect in the beginning. Every new technique has to be given a fair trial so that it could be improved upon. Here again the role of the teacher is important. The teacher can develop in the people such attitudes which are favorable to the introduction of new techniques of production and social life. The teacher, who is an active agent of cultural transmission, can play his role in bringing about harmonious conditions for social change, interims of cultural tradition.

The teacher, role in social change is that of a person who brings understanding to the people in regard to the various new scheme and benefits to be derived from them. He prepares the psychological climate favorable to new attitude and values. He helps the development of intelligent persons who provide leadership in trade, industry and community service. The teacher in a position to break the rigid habits of mind. But all these things cannot be done by these teachers who do not possess the necessary qualities of head and heart.

Need of the Study:

The society of Jammu from which the present researcher comes in mainly agricultural, rural and hence traditional. Due to green revolution in recent years, economic prosperity has suddenly grown in rural area of Jammu.

On the one hand this has been a boon to the people but on the other hand it has further thrown

the traditional society of Jammu in backward and disorganization due to increase of drinking, gambling and litigation etc.

The school teachers posted in rural schools now have a moral challenging role to play in changing, reforming, battering and modernization this sort of society in Jammu. How far these teachers enlightened about, committed to and actively engaged in their role as agents of social change in rural area of Jammu is very crucial question to which no body has yet an answer since absolutely no research studies have been done in regard to it so far. That's why the present researcher has taken up this study of the rural teachers of Jammu.

Main Objectives of the Study:

- 1) To study socio-economic and cultural background of teachers.
- 2) To study their levels of academic achievements and professional background.
- 3) To study the problems of the rural area of Jammu which they have to change being the agents of social change.
- 4) To study their degree of commitment to professionalization with regard to their role as an agents of social change.
- 5) To study their difficulties and problems in their school environment (financial, administral, political, spatial, lack) of facilities poor supervision, bureaucratic role of supervising staff and discouragement etc. and in their rural area which hinder their effective functions as agents of social change in rural area of Jammu.

Methodology:

The study was concluded with the help of questionnaire technique. A comprehensive questionnaire was prepared. It consisted of questions designed to seek information about the various aspects of information about the various aspects of the life of teachers working in rural area of Jammu. It was pre-tested on 10 teachers and their after finalized.

It was intended to collect information from 150 teachers working in the schools of rural area of Jammu. Therefore, 225 questionnaires was mailed or delivered personally.

The researcher contacted 13 headmasters, 5 MLA and 7 public and education officers and interviewed them in order to get their comments and suggestions on the role of school teachers as an agent of social change in the rural area of Jammu.

Construction of Tool:

The main purpose of the study the role of teacher as an agent of social change in rural area of Jammu. The problem was discussed with the guide and some other staff members and friends. In the light of the various opinions and suggestion given by these reference groups, a questionnaire was designed to cover the following broad areas:

- 1) Socio-Economic and Cultural Background
- 2) Academic and Professional Background
- 3) School Environment
- 4) Problems of Rural Society
- 5) Suggestions

Pre-Testing:

After the preparation of questionnaire. It was first shown to guide and pretested on 10 school teachers. Necessary corrections and modifications were made in the light of their comments and suggestions and the final draft form of the questionnaire was prepared and got printed.

Collection of Data: The researcher requested Chief Education Officer, Jammu to supply a list of middle schools in Jammu area. After getting the required list of schools, the investigator contacted the heads of this socio-economic and educational background. Post held by the respondents (table-I).

Analysis and interpretation of data

The **table-I** shows that only 23% of the respondents were working as T.G.T. and 77% were working as primary teachers.

**Table-I
Post held by the Respondents**

Post / Sex	TGT	%	Primary Teacher	%	Total	%
Male	28	20.8	86	63.7	114	84.5
Female	03	2.2	18	13.3	21	15.5
Total	31	23.00	104	77.00	135	100.00

Area of the Respondent (Table-II):

Age of the Respondents

Age group	No. of Respondents	%
18-22	11	8.1
23-27	39	28.9
28-32	37	27.4
33-37	19	14.1
38-42	20	14.8
43-47	06	4.5
48-52	03	2.2
Total	135	100.00

The **table-II** shows that 37% of the respondents are between the age of 18-27 and 79% of the respondents were below the age of 37. Only 8% of the respondents are above 42. This table indicates that most of the teachers employed in the rural area of Jammu are young.

Table-III

Sex of the Respondents

Sex	No. of Respondents	%
Male	114	84.5
Female	21	15.5
Total	135	100.00

Sex (Table-III):

Table-III shows that out of 135 respondents. There are 114 male and 21 females teachers. This table clearly indicates that the percentage of female teachers is very low (i.e. 15.6%) which is a sign of educational backward among women in the rural area of Jammu.

Marital Status (Table-IV (a)):

Table-IV (a)

Marital Status of the Respondents

Sex	Married	%	Unmarried	%	Total %
Male	109	80.8	5	3.7	84.5
Female	20	14.8	1	.7	15.5
Total	129	95.6	6	4.4	100.00

Table-IV (a) shows that about 96% of the respondent are married. There is only one unmarried female teacher. This shows that most of the respondents are married.

Table-IV (b)

Family Size of the Respondents

No. of Children	No. of Respondents	%
0-3	78	60.5
4-6	47	36.4
Above 6	4	3.1
Total	129	100.00

The number of children (Table-IV (b)):

If we see the size of the families of the respondents, we come to know that the families of almost all the respondents are planned as in the average they have 1-3 children. The analysis of item 4 in the questionnaire indicates that 90% of the respondents are in favour of family planning.

Table-V

Caste Status of the Respondents

Sex	Higher Caste	%	Schedule Caste	%	Backward Caste	%
Male	83	71.5	17	12.6	14	10.4
Female	18	13.3	01	.7	2	1.5
Total	101	74.6	18	13.3	16	11.9

Caste (Table-V):

From the analysis of table-V, we can say that about 75% of the teachers belong to higher castes and only 25% belong to schedule caste and backward class. This indicates that J&K Govt. has appointed teachers according reservation policy of the central Govt.

Table-VI

Sex	Rural	%	Urban	%
Male	104	77.00	10	7.4
Female	07	5.2	14	10.4
Total	111	82.2	24	17.8

Place of Origin (Table-VI):

Table-VI shows the distribution of respondents according to their place of origin rural and urban. As it is seen, the urban representation in the total sample is only 18%.

Taking separately according to the sex of the respondent's one can see that there are more rural male teachers and fewer rural female teachers. Women teachers with rural background are 7 out of 21 where as the number of male teachers is 104 out of 114. From this we can conclude that the rural background does not have favourable influence on women to join service. One can also make tentative statement that teaching profession is popular among the urban respondents and that is yet to reach in a considerable degree to their rural counterparts.

Income (Table-VII):Table-VII

Monthly Income of the Parents and Respondents

Income	Parents		Respondents	
	F	%	F	%
600-800	8	5.9	26	19.2
400-600	27	20.0	107	79.3
200-400	83	61.5	2	1.5
Below 200	17	12.6	-	-

In table-VII, respondents have been classified into 4 income groups. The income groups are made on the basis of the monthly income of parents and their own as reported by themselves.

This classification of respondents into various income groups indicates that most experience and interest of the respondents.

Table-VIII
Education – Backward of the Family

Member of the family	Illiterate	Primary	Middle	High / High Secondary	Graduate
Father	73	13	27	16	6
Mother	96	24	10	5	-
Husband Wife	12	37	30	40	16

Educational Background of the Family (Table-VIII):

An attempt has been made to study the educational traditions of the families of the respondents. For the purpose, the data related to the educational level of father, mother, husband/wife was collected. The data is given in table-VII.

Table-IX(a)
Educational – Backward of the respondents

Qualification	TGT	%	Primary Teacher	%	Total	%
Matric/Hr. Sec. & Tr. Certificate	-	-	80	59.3	80	59.3

BA Tr. Certificate	-	-	8	5.9	8	5.9
MA Tr. Certificate	-	-	2	1.5	2	1.5
B.A. B.Ed.	20	14.8	13	9.6	33	24.4
M.A. B.Ed.	6	4.4	-	-	6	4.4
B.A. B.Ed.	3	2.2	-	-	3	2.2
M.A. B.Ed.	2	1.5	01.	.8	3	2.3
Others	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	31	22.9	104	77.1	135	100.00

Educational background of the respondents: The respondents were required to give their academic record from the matriculation and onwards. From the **table-IX (a)** we can infer that there is one M.A., M.Ed., working as primary teacher. There are thirteen out of one hundred and four (i.e. about 13%). B.A., B.Ed. working as primary teachers in these middle schools. From the above data we can say that the teachers are over qualified and not adjusted properly shows that 69% of the respondents are still interested in their educational enhancement.

Table-IX(b)

Interest in Educational Enhancement of the respondents

Interest	TGT	%	Primary Teacher	%	Total	%
Yes	21	15.6	72	53.3	93	68.9
No	10	7.4	32	23.7	42	31.1
Total	31	23.00	104	77.00	135	100.00

Table-X (a)

Monthly Income of the Parents and Respondents

Income	Rural		Urban	
	F	%	F	%
25-29	3	2.2	-	-
20-24	3	2.2	-	-
15-19	17	12.6	3	2.2
10-14	27	20.00	12	8.9
5-9	69	51.1	16	11.9
Below 4	16	11.9	104	77
Total	135	100.00	135	100.00

In table-X (a) the respondents are classified on the basis of their experience in rural and urban area. If we calculate the mean of the two distributions then we come to know that the average experience of working in rural area is 10 years, whereas the average for the urban area comes to only 4 years.

In table-X (b), the respondents are further classified into the two categories.

Table-X (b)

Area of Interest in Teaching of the respondents

Interest area	TGT	%	Primary Teacher	%	Total	%
Rural	20	14.8	73	54.1	93	68.9
Urban	11	8.2	31	22.9	42	31.1
Total	31	23.00	104	77.00	135	100.00

Category-I shows teachers interested to work in rural area.

Category-II shows teachers interest to work in urban area.

From the table it is clear that the teachers are very much interested to work in rural area as their percentage is very high i.e. 69%.

Main Motivator (Table-XI):

On analyzing the response to the question "who mainly motivator you to join teaching profession"? We come to know that 36% of the respondents were self motivates. Only 15% were motivated by their teachers. We can 15% were motivated by their teachers. We can infer from this data that teachers generally do not advice their students to join teaching profession.

Professional Satisfaction:

Table-XII (a) shows that about 40% of the respondents are not satisfied at all with their teaching profession. Further 22% respondents are not fully satisfied with their job. 40% of the respondents which are dissatisfied have given the main reasons which are given in table-XII (b) with frequencies and percentage. First 8 of them are given more than 50% respondents of the respondents belong to lower and medium group (80%) of the respondents have their own monthly income less than 500/- and 94% of the parents income is also less than 600/- P.M.

Table-XIII:

Social Attitude Statement No.	f	%
1.	3	2.2
2.	3	2.2
3.	135	100
4.	129	95.6
5.	135	100

6.	129	95.6
7.	51	37.8

The analysis of this table reveals that the teachers in rural schools do not believe in casteism and they are not the member of any society which is affiliated with a particular caste. The teachers are very much related to social life of the rural and they try to seek their cooperation in social change. But the people are not giving them the required cooperation. Only 38% respondents revealed that they are getting the required cooperation from the society to bring about the social change.

Cultural and Religious Attitude:

There are six statements in this section which were related to the cultural and religious information. The respondents were asked to answer 'Yes' or 'No'. The statement "No" and the frequency of the respondents with % who answered "Yes" is given below:

Table-XIV: Cultural and Religious Attitude.

Statement No.	f	%
1.	73	54.1
2.	97	71.9
3.	127	94.1
4.	132	97.8
5.	135	100

Table-XIV shows that the teachers believe that in moral values and they are trying to inculcating and promoting the moral values in the rural society. They believe in religious and their cultural values.

Political Attitude:

Statements were given to have some information on the political affiliation of the respondents. On the basis of information given by respondents we can infer that although 72% respondents are the members of the teachers union but only 10% of them like to take part in political activities. However, 50% are in contact with public leaders.

Section-II:

Social, cultural, religious, political attitude and institutional climate.

Social Attitude:

The respondents were asked to mention his social background of the society in which they are living. A list of 7 statements was given and the respondents were asked to answer in "Yes" or "No". The respondent's number and the number of respondents answering a particular statement in "Yes" are given below:

Table-XV

Sections – III

Problem faced by the teachers

This section was an important section in the study. In this section the school teachers were asked to mention the problems faced by them in the process of social change. The first 4 statements were related to the problems which were due to economic development in rural area of Jammu. The respondent were asked to answer in 'yes' or 'No' . The statement number and the frequency of respondents answering in yes are given below in table –XVII

Economic Development and Knowledge of Problem.

Statement No	(Yes) F	%
1	135	100
2	119	88.2
3	135	100
4	135	100
5	129	95.6

6	98	72.6
7	135	100
8	87	64.5
9	82	60.7
10	135	100
11	135	100
12	135	100
13	105	77.8
14 (a)	135	100
(b)	108	88
(c)	135	100
(d)	108	88
(e)	84	62
(f)	121	89.6
(g)	92	68.2

Conclusions: Schools teachers working in the rural area of Jammu are not working as a successful agent of social change in Jammu. Although they are well qualified and able to bring about desired social change in rural area of Jammu, but due to various difficulties and problems they are unable to do so. Most of the teachers are not satisfied with their present economic conditions. They do not have the social respect. Society is not cooperating with teachers. They do not get proper help and guidance from education and public officers in the programme of social change. The economic development in the rural area of Jammu is also a reverse factor which is hindering the required social change and

many social evils such as drinking and dowry is increasing day by day in rural area of Jammu. If we want to bring the desired change in rural area of Jammu, then the suggestion given by teachers and others education and public officers be given due consideration.

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